

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF THE GROWTH OF MOTOR DEVELOPMENT IN GYMNASTICS

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Abstract; Motor development. Emphasizing that it is time to acquire, balance and reduce motor skills of the body; In the same process, he explained the importance of growth, maturity, readiness and learning. Physical development of a person begins before birth and continues to grow in the subsequent period. Motor development occurs after physical development occurs. previously formed as a reflex Some of the movements continue throughout life as reflexes, while some become motor skills over time with proper use of the organs. At the core of motor development, an academic discipline, is content related to views and principles related to growth, development, and motor movement.

Key words : physical education , sports gymnastics , students , development , healthy marriage style , exercises, Periods of development.

At the end of general motor development, a person's progress in movement skills is determined. Parameters such as strength, speed, coordination, balance and agility can be improved with training programs designed to improve motor skills.

Currently, the development of motor skills is given great importance and time. Although the development of motor skills depends entirely on the opportunity, motivation and training provided to the individual, it is fully accepted that these skills do not develop by themselves.

Periods of motor development

Gallahue thought of "motor development" as a stage that begins in utero and continues into later life, creating a four-stage model. Each period consists of different stages.

Periods of development

- Period of reflexive actions (0-1 years)
- The period of primitive movements (1-2 years old)
- Period of basic movements (2-7 years)
- Period of sports-related activities (7 years and older)

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Period of reflexive actions (0-1 years)

Reflex actions occur during this period. It is observed in all fetuses and babies. Thanks to reflexes, the baby collects all the information about the environment and recognizes its body. Primitive reflexes that occur during reflexive movements (sucking, searching, grasping, plantar flexion, Babinski, etc.) provide more nutritional and protective functions, while reflexive movements associated with posture (stepping, crawling, pulling, parachute, support, etc.) is like a voluntary behavior and helps the body to stand upright.

The period of primitive movements (1-2 years old)

With the development of the central nervous system, control is primarily provided by the head and trunk, and secondly by the arms and legs. Primitive movements, known as the first step of voluntary movements, are observed at the age of 0-2 years. A child's ability to stand, crawl, and sit on its own shows the importance of maturity in its development. In addition to bone, muscle and nervous system development in the first two years of life, a child's movements result from the exercise opportunities that parents provide for their babies. Although primitive movements parallel maturation, they follow a predictable sequence in their emergence. Under normal conditions, this sequence does not change, but the appearance and speed of these movements may differ in each child. Genetic and environmental influences form the basis of these changes.

The period of basic movements (2-7 years).

This is a period of increased motor development that occurs during early childhood. Here the child reveals the ability to move his body; By using body parts and the coordination between them, they acquire different and complex skills. During the period of basic movements, the child develops balance, locomotor and manipulative movement parameters and learns to perform movements first one by one, and then simultaneously. The period of basic movements creates not only the basic characteristics of the movements, but also their individual styles and characteristics. Movement models are examined one by one and combinations of these movements are revealed and movements such as running, catching, throwing, kicking, jumping and rolling are combined. Movements form the basis of many sports networks. For example; Throwing something forward is a basic movement in sports like volleyball or tennis. The development of skills paves the way for sports activities.

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Period of sports-related activities (7 years and older)

This stage is a continuation of the period of main actions. Actions in this part are goal-oriented. The skills acquired during the main activities can be combined with the rules and become joint activities. Explain with an example; Jumping and jumping skills learned during basic movements can be translated into a structured jump rope game that requires cooperation in this section.

The characteristics of the movement period associated with sports are;

- A high rate of growth is observed in achievement until adolescence.
- In order for the level of motor development to be perfect, it is important that basic movement skills are at their maximum.
- When starting to engage in sports activities aimed at ensuring the child's development, it is necessary to review the period of basic movements and work on mature movement skills.
 - In order to acquire sports skills in the body, it is necessary to pay attention to the period of basic movements. During this time, skills should be consciously taught to the child.
 - Coaches should prepare training programs based on the ability and development of athletes.
 - Competitions can be organized for the motivation needed for athletes to master these skills very well and perform them perfectly.

Competitions are of great importance in the life of athletes. Success in competitions depends on experience.

Effects of gymnastics on motor characteristics

Nowadays, when technology is a complete part of life, children's mobility is limited to computer games, TV and phones.

Children's desire to be in constant motion, which is necessary for their physical, mental and emotional development, is consciously or unconsciously inhibited.

Children who play sports regularly develop personally and physically. Gymnastics plays an important role in the physical and motor development of children.

Regular participation in physical activity, gymnastics or training benefits body mass (body weight, fat to muscle ratio), bone mineralization and density, muscle development and strength, and cardiorespiratory system development. If gymnastics

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is done systematically, the body will remain physically healthy. This fitness improves endurance, muscle strength, flexibility, body composition and cardiovascular system. movements such as falling. equipment. All movements that make up gymnastics contribute to the child's cardio-respiratory system, muscle strength and endurance.

Various bridging exercises using different parts of the body, jumping exercises and stretching exercises to cool down the body at the end of the training will help improve the flexibility of the body.

In addition, regular participation in programmed training or physical activity ensures that athletes become healthy individuals. Being healthy is important in child development. This can be achieved almost with gymnastic exercises. As a result of research; The need for physical activity is understood and it has been shown that people who exercise in a programmed way have fewer health problems in later life.

Motor characteristics. Motor characteristics are strength, endurance, speed, flexibility and dexterity. The key to success in all sports is the specifics of the equipment required for the sport being used. Motor characteristics vary depending on the body's mobility and efficiency level. It is not acquired, it is innate and developed. The development of these characteristics occurs after a regular training program. It is determined by tests and strength checks that determine the level of development. The development of basic motor skills in all areas of sports is parallel to the training program that we implement.

Classification of coordination. It is divided into general and special coordination. However, it is divided into subheadings such as closed, open, combined, coarse and fine coordination.

Coordination by sport

General Coordination: This is coordination that involves the whole body and is for all sports without being specific to a specific sport. This sets the stage for special coordination. Once general coordination is improved, performing specific coordination exercises will benefit the athlete's performance.

Specific Coordination: It is the application of the branch's unique core characteristics and technical skills by creating a targeted training program.

Motor skills. This means that a person is experienced and fully skilled in a subject. To implement this form of movement, it is necessary to learn. For example, walking and running are easy for adults, but skills are important for a 14-month-old

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baby. In this context, a motor skill can be defined as "a series of actions performed correctly as a result of a combination of experience and learning." Studies focusing on the acquisition and development of motor skills are useful. Due to these studies, the necessary wishes and needs of the child are met.

Motor learning. This is evidence of increased success in performance as a result of mastering actions developed with experience. The fact that the skills acquired by the body by repeating them many times supports the understanding of the achievements to be learned, which is useful for motor learning and facilitates the process.

Development of gross (Cross) motor skills . Gross motor development is a condition in which many parts of the child's body are in motion at the same time. For example; Gross motor skills include crawling, walking, running, jumping, or jumping. All skills related to walking and postural control develop during infancy. Although the neural pathways involved in a child's walking are formed much earlier, babies usually learn to walk by the age of one. Each child may have individual differences in this skill stage. The period when a child develops gross motor movements such as running, jumping, grasping an object, etc. is parallel to the period of basic motor movements.

Fine motor development

These are skills that are completely independent of each other and involve very small actions. This includes skill exercises such as the child passing a toy from one hand to another, trying to write or draw using hand-eye coordination. Skills such as tying a net, tying a belt, shaping a piece of clay, cutting an object with scissors ensure that children work their small muscles in a coordinated manner. The development of these skills is mainly observed in preschool age. While a child's ability to hear, see, smell, taste, and touch at an adult level begins in early childhood, preschoolers can take off their clothes and tie their shoelaces, which and provides important skills in use. consists of small muscles. For example, a four-year-old child can perceive and understand detailed situations in pictures and use his perceptual skills to coordinate his pictures with body movements. In order to have hand-eye and muscle coordination, it is important that the movements are in harmony with each other and move in a coordinated manner.

By the age of three, children can hold some small objects for a short time using their index finger and thumb. But this does not indicate that fine motor skills have

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improved. For example, if they see the right place to insert a broken puzzle piece, but can't place it, they usually try to force it into place or end it by hitting hard. Four-year-old children arrange toy blocks and try to build a tower. By age five, their motor skills are more developed and they can move their bodies in a coordinated manner. Clear and rapid development of fine motor development occurs mainly in early childhood. They can draw with finger paint, put on and take off their own shoes, spread food on bread using the right knife, and make drawings about the human body. In addition, they can use their senses and coordinate their hands and feet and write some letters or names.

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